

The Somalia Conflicts, African Reversal Democracy and Governance. The Case of West Africa

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Abstract

The conflict of Somalia has grassroot factors and complexities since last three decades in the absence of strong central government controlled the entire country, the complexity including Instability, and competition for resources. The war erupted in the late 1980s after the ousting of the Siad Barre regime, resulting in a power vacuum and the emergence of warlords. The situation deteriorated in the 1990s with the rise of Islamist groups, particularly Al-Shabaab, which continues to fight against the Somali interim government and international forces. for the case of west African countries, ten countries with the lowest (World Population Review, 2024) Human Development Index scores. Countries such as these are faced with widespread poverty, poor education, lack of adequate health care and, perhaps most importantly, stable governments International Monetary Fund reports show that these countries also have some of the lowest annual rates of GDP¹ per capita in the world. This policy brief detailed the grassroot of Somalia conflict and in generally African democracy and governance for the cases of west Africa. The Paper has structurally two section which are the first section presents the conflict of Somalia, the grassroot and the possible options of resolving. In the next the paper discussed African democracy reversal and governance management in practical case. The paper has recommendation and feedback on research-based evidence. In the context of Somalia peace and conflict there were several efforts for peace and stability have been ongoing, involving various local and global stakeholders, but the country still faces significant challenges, including persistent violence, humanitarian crises, and political fragmentation. The African democratic journey has not been without its share of obstacles, despite these achievements. Sometimes progress has been impeded by instances of electoral irregularities, political instability, and corruption. Long-term authoritarian government has hindered the growth of democratic institutions in some countries. This sit-tight-in-power syndrome has been the bane of democratic leadership and electoral process in Africa (Aremu, 2024). The objective this brief policy is to understand the grassroot conflict of Somalia and its consequence and the beyond to identify African democracy and governance for the case of West African as constitutional changes, term power extension and reversal democracy.

Keywords: *Conflict, Democracy, Governance, Power.*

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¹ GDP represented Gross domestic product and describes the monetary measure of the market value of all the final goods and services produced and rendered in a specific time by a country or countries. GDP is often used to measure the economic health of a country or region.

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Introduction

Somalia Conflict

There are different types of conflict in Africa. Some African conflicts are based on resource conflict, interstate conflict, land conflict (Arbitrary borders), political power, ethnicity, corruptions and negative effect of external debt burden. Looking at the nature of those conflicts some left by the colonial to Africa. It identifies African conflicts (Somalia), practical the case of Somalia, reflect the current condition of Somalia.

The history of Africa as a continent is complete with conflict. (Alabi, 2006:41). One may even assert that the major current runs through Africa, from North to South, East to West and Central is conflicts. Since the 1960s, series of conflicts had taken place in Africa. Examples include Sudan (1995-1990), Chad (1965-85), Angola since 1974, Liberia (1980- 2003), Nigeria (1967-70), Somalia (1991-2000) and Burundi, Rwanda and Sierra Leone (1991-2001).

African conflict has also witnessed several recurrent border and inter- state conflicts notable among which are the following:

- Nigeria- Cameroon dispute over Bakassi peninsular since the 1970's;
- Algeria- Morocco conflict over the Atlas Mountains area in October 1963;
- Eritrea- Ethiopian crisis between 1962 and 1979;
- Somalia-Ethiopia` dispute of 1964 to 1978 over the Ugandan desert region;
- Chad- Libya crisis of 1980- 1982;
- Kenya- Somalia border war of 1963 -1967 in which Somalia aimed at recovering its lost; territories including the Northern frontier district of Kenya;
- Tanzania-Uganda crisis in 1978-79 (Aremu, 2010).

The Prime Conflict of Somalia

In looking at the Somali people as far back as the twelfth century and as late as 1800, both within the Horn and beyond, generally being only nominally governed also suggests ever-changing styles of rule, boundaries, and jurisdictional areas, and yet the Somali people did not just adapt but often flourished. Moreover, to be so organized socially and politically within their agnatic clan system, generally ruling themselves more by consensus than conflict contributed greatly towards making them particularly independent and self-reliant (Fox, 2015). the prime factors of Somalia conflict comprising political power, resource sharing, clan dispute on the base of land, borderline dispute (Somaliland and Puntland) and distribution of political seats.

Actors Involved Somalia Conflict

Internal Actors

Somalia in three decades there was a conflict between the people of Somalia, this conflict tackles the development of the state including government infrastructure, Law and order, peace, and security. When the central government of Somalia was thrown out in 1991, functional clan leader become power and then several attempts of international community bring reconciliation process in Somalia and then build transitional government of Somalia. Later the transitional government converted to Federal Government of Somalia (FGS). The conflict parties of Somalia among three actors which are clans, political leaders, federal government and the extremist terrorist organization Al-Shabab. Later, the clans have removed and become party of the government, now the conflict is between two sides which are the federal government of Somalia and Al- Shabaab (the terrorist organization).

There is external actor that are involved the conflict of Somalia which are special interest. Because Somalia is long coast and is one of the largest coasts in Africa. Connected with the Indian ocean and red

sea, this is a strategic geographical location, this is biggest reasons that some big countries are much interested in Somalia.

To adequately understand the conflict and identify its implications for Somalia, it is imperative to examine the processes or factors that underlie Somalia's highly complicated and protracted conflict (Dersso, 2009).

Somalia is one of the longest African conflicts for the last three decades, since the destruction of Somali central government, this conflict is not a sudden and inexplicable eruption. It has long triggered factors including nepotism, tribalism and unequal share to the government resource. Dictatorship and undemocratic administration among the society. This root cause erupted and destroyed the central government of Somalia.

External Actors

Somali people from nomadic community with base of traditional norms of peace and conflict, during solving conflict among the Somali people, the traditional elders were bringing the affected sides and proposed their concerns about the issues of disagreed. External actors were involved (International Actors) and not restore the peace and stability. Apart from the external actor, there were several attempts of international community want to bring peace and stability in Somalia.

A further complicating factor that those involved in conflict and peacekeeping must struggle with is the multiple external dimensions, and external actors involved in, the conflict. This is an equally important dimension of the Somali conflict that has received inadequate attention but is increasingly playing an important part in the ongoing conflict. The external dimension of the conflict and the involvement of external actors is attributable to at least three factors. The first one, is the security concern that the conflict in Somalia raises for some of Somalia's neighbors, particularly Ethiopia. The second is the power struggle for dominance in the Horn of Africa between various countries. Thirdly, there is the war against terrorism (Dersso, 2009).

The Impact of Somalia Conflict

The conflicts in the continent had lasting negative impact on the socio- economic development of Africa because socio- economic development cannot be sustained in an environment damaged with violence, instability and insecurity. Somalia one of the countries backflash for three decades in conflict, the consequence effect largely Somali community in domestically and those are in the abroad, the outcome of Somalia conflict reflected on poor of infrastructural development, high rate of unemployment, death and loss of lives and refugee and internally displace people:

- Conflict can result the recurrence to violence facing major challenges of destruction of infrastructural development of state, one of the impacts of Somalia conflicts is the backwardness of infrastructure, facilities, educations and service delivery of the government to the citizens. The whole country become poor economic income per capita while the countries is under conflict tension between parties.
- Conflicts in Africa (Somalia) have combined to compound the problem of unemployment in the continent. Today, Somalia is one of the high rates of unemployment, particularly of youth is a major source of concern. It has no growing at an annual employment rate and major unemployment rate is high.
- Many Somalia people lost their lives in conflict between parties, example, A great number of young, old, male, female, civilians, have lost their lives to various conflicts on Somalia during the last 30 years of conflict contested different actors those are in local and international.
- One of the attendant effects conflicts in Somalia is the emergence of numerous numbers of displaced persons who have become refugee in different nations across the continent and other countries in the world and become homeless and refugee.

Policy Recommendation to Somalia Conflict

This policy brief has suggested insight recommendations for the African reversal democracy, governance and the conflict of Somalia and West African reversal democracy and governance.

Strong Institutions and Committed Leadership: Somalia needs committed, strong institution, strong leader that will lead by example and act as good, responsible and responsive to all component of the country, in terms of Leadership, it is important to have committed leadership that can deliver the willingness of the people.

Equal and Justice Distribution of Resource: Somalia leaders must ensure an equal justice distribution of resources among the various settlement countries. Most conflict came from the scarce resource and their distribution, this policy recommended resource of the country should be based on the equal distribution among the various community across the country, this can be lead equal justices of resource distribution.

Promotion of Rule of Law: Somalia leaders should also attempt to promote the rule of law, transparency and responsiveness to the citizens. This involves equal access to justice by all citizens irrespective of their status, respect of court decisions by the government and influential, and conduct of free and fair periodic elections in democratic approach. This point can create trust among the community and their leadership, leader should promote rule of law.

Protection of Fundamental Human rights and Citizen Protection rights: Somalia leaders should also promote, Human rights, protect and guarantee the fundamental human rights of citizens. In particular, the fundamental rights of freedom of speech, association should be guaranteed. People exercise their rights into respect with the law and legal framework of the state. People should be free to assess and criticize the performance of government without fear of persecution.

Poverty Eradication and Create Wealth of the Country: The poverty is the root of all evils in Africa. Somalia is one of them, Somalia people need from their leaders to have poverty eradication and create wealth mechanism which can be removed the poverty and destitutions.

Quality Education: Somalia leaders should give priority to quality education during setting the budget and national plans. The importance of education to the socio- economic development of a nation has been well articulated in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), The national plan of education should be lined with SDG.

Employment of Youth: Somalia leaders should be encouraged farming through mechanized agriculture. Modern farm implements and technology should be provided for farmers at cheap prices. Eradicating of hunger problems, this will no doubt equally enhance the economic empowerment of youth employment in nation wise.

West African Case for Democracy and Governance

In the early of 1990 Africa has been significant change of democracy in terms of politics and elections. Movement led by the world Bank and IMF has introduced an instrumental factor of democracy and governance. This tool was governance for the modification democracy and removal of coups and then turned-on democratic principles and elections. This Era was institutionalized and democracy in Africa.

Many civilian and military dictatorships have fallen, paving the way for the establishment of rule of law based on democracy, transparency, accountability, participations, responsiveness of governance systems characterized by constitutionalism and constitutional government, including reforms such as election term limits. However, many of these countries still struggle to deepen and institutionalize democracy and deal effectively and fully with government impunity, particularly that which is associated with the abuse of executive power and the violation of human rights.

In west African during this time, the leaders of some west African countries change their term of elections, and this caused poor performance of governance and leadership failure.

According to the African Center for Strategic Studies, since 2015, the leader of 13 African countries have escaped or overseen and further weakening of term limits restrictions that has been place in their countries. Those leaders want to extend their term of power, and this was created undemocratic tension in those countries. For example, the president of Côte d'Ivoire Alassane Ouattara was among those leaders seemingly barred from standing for the presidency this election cycle by the constitution's two term limit, argued in August 2020 that his first two mandates do not count because the limits were created by the constitution that was adopted in 2016 (Brookings Institution, n.d.).

Result of Failure of Electoral Democracy - Reversal Democracy in West Africa

It is also up to the citizens to translate into reality the use of democracy, justice, peace, fair play and courage. It is only under these conditions that African political life will no longer borrow its vocabulary from the "loser wins" perspective (the fact that those in power, usually dictators, reject the results of the elections and are tempted to remain in power by force, ignoring the choice made by most of the population, free and fair elections). Fortunately, democracy in Africa also offers us edifying examples where the real losers refuse to yield to the temptation of the "loser wins" one. Those at least know that power and honors are at the service of the people and not at the service of the false. Barack Obama, who left power (after two well-deserved terms, recalled in his speech in Accra: "History is on the side of these courageous Africans, not in the camp of those who use coup or modify the constitutions to remain in power. Africa does not need strong men but strong institution (Kibangou, 2018).

According to my analysis in Africa (West Africa) it is true that African need strong institution, but I believe also Africa need strong men under the rule of law and governance principle for following the constitution of the country. Here is the result of the failure of electoral democracy in Africa based on West African countries - Reversal of democracy in West Africa:

- The Guinea farmer president, Apha Conde has attempted to change the constitution to be able to run for a third term in the office and this was caused huge unpopular and constitutional crisis. The coup of Guinea was related on the issue of elections, and this was the result of poor governance and undemocratic approach (Ajala, 2023).
- Mali has experienced two coups within nine months. The first one was in August 2020, when President Ibrahim Boubacar Keita was ousted by the military led by Colonel Assimi Goïta. The coup came after three months of protest by Malians against irregularities in the parliamentary elections, while simultaneously demanding security, respect for democratic norms and the provision of basic services.
- In Burkina Faso, the country's citizens were frustrated with the civilian regime, which was accused of corruptions and nepotism. According to the Institute for Security Studies, trust in government had been declining since 2017 due to lack of good governance.
- In this region of West Africa increased spotlight on the corruption and lack of development, poor service delivery and the undemocratic power of the country those factors caused the population to become immoral while the leadership has done illegal action against the governance and democracy.
- Another important of west Africa reversal democracy and the failure democracy is the involvement of colonial. Because colonial involved in the elections of those countries as indirect, sometimes they may support illegal candidate want to extend his term of elections, just they look at their interest.

In the analysis of above points reversal, the democracy in west Africa and the failure result of those countries. According to the military coup, unconstitutional acts, corruptions, nepotism stated those countries has not good governance or proper governance in terms of institutional framework, it obviously that those countries has not governance practice in term of legal framework, provision of legal mandate and other regulatory framework of the institutions.

The Failure Element of Democracy in West Africa

Democracy is viewed by many as a system of government by the whole population or all eligible members of a state, typically through elected representatives. Oxford English Dictionary put it this way.

It is a system of government in which all the people of state or polity are involved in making decisions about its affairs, typically by voting to elect representative to a parliament or similar assembly.

Diamond & Leonardo (2004) assets that democracy consists of four key elements, these include:

- A political system for choosing and replacing the government through free and fair elections.
- The active participation of the people, as citizens in politics and civic life.
- Protection of the human rights of all citizens.
- A rule of law, in which the laws and procedures apply equally to all citizens (Abur, 2018).

According to the above statement, it true that democracy from the people want to elect their representative in free and fair elections. Those elected people should use a good behavior of democratic principles, in the below discussion there are some failure elements of West African democracy that cause the West African reversal democracy:

1. There is no accountability among the government and citizens, this is one of the failures of democracy in West African, as well as this is one of the reason of leaders extended their term of elections and want to hold power.
2. One of the outcomes of failure democracy (reversal) in West Africa is no responsiveness from the government to citizens in term of service delivery.
3. Element of failure democracy including, irrespective of Human right and human dignity, most of those country is arrested people illegally, this can bring failure of democracy and freedom of speech.
4. Element of failure democracy are, arbitration of arrest, lack of freedom of association, no participation and expression of ideas, exclusivity of small group to exploit the rest of others.

Conclusion

Constitutional Change in West African Countries and Their Consequences

African leaders like to change the constitution after their term of elections ended. This change of constitution is illegal. Some West African Leaders attempt to change the constitutions like Guinea, the outcome of this change resulted:

- The regions of West Africa are undergoing a period of political confusion and democratic collapse. AU intervenes not to changes the constitutions and emphasis of democratizations.
- The main reasons for doing change constitutions are extended the power, AU and other regional organization like ECOWAS rejected this bid.
- Regional and continental organizations must take a strong stand against constitutional manipulations by incumbent presidents and ensure that democracies deliver dividends to the people.

Policy Recommendations- to West African Democracy and Governance

The above section has discussed result of reversal democracy in west Africa, In terms of elections and democracy, and the failure element of democracy in West Africa and the issues of constitutional change and their impact to the country development. It is recommended to apply intentionally the following policy recommendations.

Effective rule of Law: (The country should be constitutional country): it is important to fulfill the constitutional mandates for democracy and governance and create strong commitment of safeguard of democracy and elections, the effectiveness of Rule of Law and governance.

Transparency: Government Leaders must create a comprehensive platform of Transparency (independent commission) among the people on basis of Transparency of governance.

Participations: during policy development and programs of the government, government leader should create a detailed plan lined with the constitutions, citizens should have an access during the creating of Public Policies and participation.

Effective and Efficiency: In the sense of public service delivery and government programs of promoting to citizen's wellbeing and existence of good life, government leader initiates effective platform of service delivery and equal distribution to service across the country, this policy factors can bring stability, growth and development of citizens needs of public service.

Equity and Equality: all citizens have an equal rights under the Law and equality among the resource, during setting policies, rule and guidelines, government leaders should bear that this factor can take part the development of country justice system and all the local laws should promote this factor and introduce the community to be aware in order to seek their rights, this policy factor will bring good governance and effective democracy.

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